

Донецької області від 15.10.2022 № 312/02/24-2022.

4. Яковлева Т. К. Особливості протидії кримінальним правопорушенням, що вчиняються неповнолітніми на території проведення операції Об'єднаних сил. Протидія кримінальним правопорушенням на території проведення ООС: матеріали Всеукраїнської науково-практичної конференції (м. Маріуполь, 22 жовтня 2021 року). Ред кол.: О. Волобуєва, А. Данилевський, В. Котова. Маріуполь, 2021. С 114-117.

5. Регіональна програма профілактики правопорушень серед дітей на території Донецької області на 2019 – 2022 роки: розпорядження Голови ОДА від 23.11.2018 № 1410/5-18. Офіційний сайт Донецької обласної державної адміністрації. URL: <https://dn.gov.ua/storage/app/sites/1/publicinfo/1410-18.pdf>.

ORLOV Viktor,

Deputy Head of the Department for Investigation of Crimes Committed in the Conditions of Armed Conflict of the Main Department of the National Police in Donetsk region, PhD in Law

ASPECTS OF COUNTERACTING THE INVOLVEMENT OF PRIVATE MILITARY COMPANIES IN ARMED AGGRESSION AGAINST UKRAINE

The understanding that the armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine has been going on since February 20, 2014, and the hybrid war against our country has been going on since the Day of Declaration of its Independence, leads to the conclusion about the need for an early and inevitable bringing to international legal responsibility of the aggressor country. One of the means of hybrid warfare that Russia has been using on the territory of Ukraine since 2014 is private military companies (hereinafter - PMCs).

The uncertain status of PMCs in international law has allowed the Russian Federation to commit war crimes and crimes against humanity on the territory of Ukraine with the "hands" of PMC "employees". Thus, on 23.12.2021, SBU investigators served in absentia a notice of suspicion to the head of the Russian PMC "Wagner" of committing an encroachment on the territorial integrity and inviolability of Ukraine, as well as waging an aggressive war of crimes (Part 3 of Art. 110, Part 5 of Art. 27, Part 2 of Art. 28, Part 2 of Art. 437 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) [1]. But the customer of all crimes - Russia, headed by the highest military-political leadership, is currently impossible to bring to justice. The issue of bringing them to international legal responsibility for human rights violations is undoubtedly extremely urgent.

PMCs operate in the absence of international legal norms that would define their status and responsibility. In fact, they are not subjects of international law and bearers of

the obligation under the UN Charter not to use force in international relations. Adopted international documents - the Montreux Document (2008) and the International Code of Conduct for Private Security Companies (2010) are declarative in nature, they do not contain mechanisms for bringing to justice members of PMCs and the aggressor country that involves them in armed conflict.

In accordance with international humanitarian law (hereinafter - IHL), the status of PMCs in armed conflict is determined on a case-by-case basis, based on the functions they perform. Also, according to IHL, PMC "employees" cannot be considered combatants, and taking into account some tasks performed by Russian PMCs in Ukraine, their status can be defined as spies [2]. Therefore, PMC "employees" enjoy neither respect nor protection of international humanitarian law.

These legal gaps allowed the terrorist country Russia to use PMCs to carry out sabotage and terrorist operations, to carry out the armed seizure of the territories of Ukraine in February 2014 and to continue to use these armed formations in the full-scale invasion of our country on 24.02.2022.

Official state bodies and media use such epithets as mercenaries, militants, terrorists, armed organized criminal groups to define Russian PMCs. The most numerous among them is PMC "Wagner" (Wagner Group), and after 2021 PMC "League", its number is more than 8 thousand people, has small arms, heavy weapons, tanks and combat aircraft. Over the past decade, the top military-political leadership of the Russian Federation has used them in armed conflicts in Syria, Sudan, Mozambique, Libya, the Central African Republic and Venezuela, where Wagner PMC fighters have committed brazen war crimes and crimes against humanity.

On 25.11.2021, in its Resolution, the European Parliament recognized PMC Wagner as an agent of the Russian state, and noted that Russia is responsible for the financing, training, management and operational command of these paramilitary groups and should be held accountable for international crimes committed by its proxy (Wagner Group) [3].

The conclusions of the European institution are based on the fact that states are responsible for violations of human rights legislation. If the guarantor of human rights is the state, then attempts to shift the focus of attention from states to entities whose status is not defined in international law (POC) may undermine the idea of the state as a key responsible institution, weaken the ability of states to cope with threats themselves [4, p. 145].

Thus, in the absence of international legal criminalization, individual "employees" of the PMC are criminally liable only under national legislation as civilians.

The lack of transparency in the activities of Russian PMCs leads to human rights violations, therefore, the introduction of the mechanism of responsibility of the aggressor state for the activities of PMCs will allow to demand from the states to provide the victims of such violations with appropriate remedies for compensation for damages.

The analysis gives grounds to conclude that the failure to urgently adopt the relevant

international legal norms will lead to further insidious use of PMCs by Russians, as evidenced by the information about the arrival of 130 employees of the PMC "Liga" (former PMC "Wagner") (with personal weapons and ammunition) in Minsk on 20.09.2022 to involve them in organizing provocations on the Ukrainian border [5].

The international community must immediately find ways to counteract hybrid armies - PMCs, right now there is an urgent need to define a clear status of PMCs under international law, the main form of legal regulation of PMCs should be international treaties that will establish standards of legal status of PMCs and their employees. The norms of international humanitarian law need to be amended to define the status of a "member of a PMC armed formation".

To fulfill these tasks, it is necessary to create a *single international body to control the activities of PMCs*, whose powers should include: establishing unified rules for the creation and operation of PMCs; control over the activities and financing of PMCs; prohibition of the activities of private military companies in aggressor countries; liquidation of PMCs in case of their illegal activities. However, the main function of this institution should be to promptly and inevitably bring the aggressor country to international legal responsibility in case of using PMCs in hybrid wars and to ensure compensation for victims of human rights violations caused by PMCs.

Referens

1. SBU serves suspicion notice to head of Russian military company "Wagner": he commanded combat actions against ATO forces near Debaltseve. URL: <https://ssu.gov.ua/novyny/sbu-oholosyla-pidozru-kerivnyku-rosiiskoi-viiskovoi-kompanii-vahner-komanduvav-boiovyimy-diiamy-proty-syl-ato-pid-debaltsevym> (date of access: 04.10.2022).

2. Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I), of 8 June 1977. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_199#Text (accessed 25.09.2022).

3. Human rights violations by private military and security companies, particularly the Wagner Group. URL: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/CRE-9-2021-11-25-ITM-006-02_EN.html (accessed 01.10.2022).

4. Private military companies in the conditions of hybrid warfare. *Juris Europensis Scientia*. 2020. Issue 3. C. 144-150. DOI <https://doi.org/10.32837/chern.v0i3.116>.

5. Russian mercenaries are preparing provocations along the Belarusian-Ukrainian border. URL: <https://sprotyv.mod.gov.ua/2022/09/24/rosijski-najmanczi-gotuyut-provokacziyi-vzdovzh-bilorusko-ukrayinskogo-kordonu/> (accessed 08.10.2022).